

The quantum potential based on the G-dynamics of quantum covariant Hamiltonian system

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Abstract

Inspired by the geomentum operator and the G-dynamics of quantum covariant Hamiltonian system (QCHS) defined by the quantum covariant Poisson bracket (QCPB) theory, we reconsider the quantum potential as part of the Schrödinger equation by using the generalized gradient operator, and then it naturally leads to the geometric potential only associated with the scalar function as a environment variable, we present the geometric quantum potential as an extension of the quantum potential, it naturally includes the imaginary geomenergy as a part of it, meanwhile, we can deduce the quantum potential by using the imaginary geomenergy in a given condition.

1 Introduction

1.1 Quantum potential

The quantum potential in its interpretation as an information potential which acts on a quantum particle is a central concept of the de Broglie-Bohm formulation of quantum mechanics, initially introduced by David Bohm in 1952 [1, 2]. In the framework of the de Broglie-Bohm theory, the quantum potential is a term within the Schrödinger equation which acts to guide the movement of quantum particles. The quantum potential approach introduced by Bohm provides a formally more complete exposition of the idea presented by Louis de Broglie: de Broglie had postulated in 1926 that the wave function represents a pilot wave which guides a quantum particle. Quantum potential as part of the Schrödinger equation, the Schrödinger equation

$$\sqrt{-1}\hbar\frac{\partial\psi}{\partial t} = \widehat{H}^{(cl)}\psi = \left(-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\nabla^2 + V\right)\psi \quad (1)$$

is rewritten using the polar form for the wave function $\psi = A^{(b)}\exp(\sqrt{-1}S/\hbar)$ with real-valued functions $A^{(b)}$ and S , where $A^{(b)}$ is the amplitude (absolute value) of the wave function

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ψ , and S/\hbar its phase. This yields two equations: from the imaginary and real part of the Schrödinger equation follow the continuity equation and the quantum Hamilton-Jacobi equation respectively. The real part of the Schrödinger equation in polar form yields a modified Hamilton-Jacobi equation [3, 4]

$$\frac{\partial S}{\partial t} = - \left(\frac{|\nabla S|^2}{2m} + V + Q^{(cl)} \right),$$

also referred to as quantum Hamilton-Jacobi equation. It differs from the classical Hamilton-Jacobi equation only by the term

$$Q^{(cl)} = - \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{\nabla^2 A^{(b)}}{A^{(b)}}.$$

which is called quantum potential.

The wave function is a function of the degrees of freedom corresponding to some maximal set of commuting observables. Once such a representation is chosen, the wave function can be derived from the quantum state. The state of such a particle is completely described by its wave function as a complex-valued, $\psi(x, t)$ in which x is position and time t . The wave function is usually written in the form

$$\psi = \sqrt{\rho(r, t)} e^{\sqrt{-1}S(r, t)/\hbar}$$

where ρ is the probability density, a probability amplitude $\sqrt{\rho(r, t)}$ is a complex number used in describing the behaviour of systems.

2 Generalized geometric commutator and geomutator

Let a and b be any two operators, their commutator is formally defined by $[a, b]_{cr} = ab - ba$. Let a and b be any elements of any algebra, or any operators, their generalized geometric commutator is formally defined by the following.

Definition 1 (GGC). [5] *A generalized geometric commutator (GGC) of arity two a, b is formally given by*

$$[a, b] = [a, b]_{cr} + G(s, a, b)$$

The geomutator is

$$G(s, a, b) = a[s, b]_{cr} - b[s, a]_{cr}$$

satisfying $G(s, a, b) = -G(s, b, a)$, where s is a geometric structure function given by domain.

Note that in this definition above, the scalar function s as a geometric structure function can be arbitrarily chosen on purpose for a general research. As we mentioned, the scalar function s is only relied on the domain, manifold, algebra structure, space, etc.

2.1 The QCPB theory and quantum geometric bracket

In this section, we begin with some basic concepts of quantum covariant Poisson bracket defined by the generalized geometric commutator, and quantum geometric bracket is defined by the geomutator. In quantum mechanics, quantum Poisson brackets $[\hat{f}, \hat{g}]_{QPB}$ is the commutator of two operators \hat{f} , \hat{g} defined as $[\hat{f}, \hat{g}]_{QPB} = \hat{f}\hat{g} - \hat{g}\hat{f}$.

Definition 2 (QCPB). [5] *The QCPB is generally defined as*

$$[\hat{f}, \hat{g}] = [\hat{f}, \hat{g}]_{QPB} + G(s, \hat{f}, \hat{g})$$

in terms of quantum operator \hat{f} , \hat{g} , where $G(s, \hat{f}, \hat{g}) = -G(s, \hat{g}, \hat{f})$ is called quantum geometric bracket.

It is zero if and only if \hat{f} and \hat{g} covariant commute, i.e. $[\hat{f}, \hat{g}] = 0$. It is remarkable to see that the QCPB representation admits a dynamical geometric bracket formula on the manifold. Note that structural function s represents the background property of spacetime.

Definition 3 (quantum geometric bracket). [5] *The quantum geometric bracket is*

$$G(s, \hat{f}, \hat{g}) = \hat{f}[s, \hat{g}]_{QPB} - \hat{g}[s, \hat{f}]_{QPB}$$

where s represents the globally condition of space.

As a consequence of the precise formulation of the quantum geometric bracket, the QCPB is completely written as

$$[\hat{f}, \hat{g}] = [\hat{f}, \hat{g}]_{QPB} + \hat{f}[s, \hat{g}]_{QPB} - \hat{g}[s, \hat{f}]_{QPB}$$

2.2 Quantum covariant Hamiltonian system and the covariant dynamics

In this section, we will briefly review the entire theoretical framework of quantum covariant Hamiltonian system defined by the quantum covariant Poisson bracket completely given by the previous paper [5].

Definition 4 (QCHS). [5] *The QCHS defined by QCPB in terms of quantum operator \hat{f} , \hat{H} is generally given by*

$$[\hat{f}, \hat{H}] = [\hat{f}, \hat{H}]_{QPB} + G(s, \hat{f}, \hat{H})$$

where $G(s, \hat{f}, \hat{H})$ is quantum geobacket .

By using the quantum covariant Hamiltonian system, it directly leads to the emergence of the covariant dynamics including the generalized Heisenberg equation, G-dynamics. More precisely, the time covariant evolution of any observable \hat{f} in the covariant dynamics is given by both the generalized Heisenberg equation of motion and G-dynamics.

Theorem 1 (The covariant dynamics). [5] *The covariant dynamics, the generalized Heisenberg equation, G-dynamics can be formally formulated as*

The covariant dynamics: $\frac{\mathcal{D}\hat{f}}{dt} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{-1}\hbar} [\hat{f}, \hat{H}]$

The generalized Heisenberg equation: $\frac{d\hat{f}}{dt} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{-1}\hbar} [\hat{f}, \hat{H}]_{QPB} - \frac{1}{\sqrt{-1}\hbar} \hat{H} [s, \hat{f}]_{QPB}$

G-dynamics: $\hat{w} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{-1}\hbar} [s, \hat{H}]_{QPB}$.

respectively, where $\frac{\mathcal{D}}{dt} = \frac{d}{dt} + \hat{w}$ is covariant time operator, and \hat{H} is the Hamiltonian and $[\cdot, \cdot]$ denotes the GGC of two operators.

Based on the G-dynamics, the imaginary geomenergy can be completely defined, we can better give a presentation for the covariant dynamics, ect.

Definition 5. [5] *The imaginary geomenergy is defined by $E^{(Im)}(\hat{w}) = \sqrt{-1}\hbar\hat{w}$, where \hat{w} is the G-dynamics.*

As mentioned above, the imaginary geomenergy as an energy operator induced by the G-dynamics leads to the energy eigenvalues equation with the energy eigenvalues.

As a result, thusly, then a dynamical variable \hat{f} with the geomenergy defined above, then covariant dynamics is rewritten in the form

$$\sqrt{-1}\hbar\frac{\mathcal{D}}{dt}\hat{f} = [\hat{f}, \hat{H}] = \sqrt{-1}\hbar\frac{d}{dt}\hat{f} + \hat{f}E^{(Im)}(\hat{w})$$

As a consequence of the imaginary geomenergy, we can say that imaginary geomenergy is a new kind of Hamiltonian operator. Obviously, if the covariant equilibrium equation $[\hat{f}, \hat{H}] = 0$ holds, then it yields $\frac{d}{dt}\hat{f} + \hat{f}\hat{w} = 0$ or this covariant equilibrium formula in the form shows $\frac{d}{dt}\hat{f} = -\hat{f}\hat{w}$, accordingly, \hat{f} is said to be a quantum covariant conserved quantity.

Since the G-dynamics has been discovered as an independent dynamics to picture the quantum mechanics, we have studied its precise properties. More precisely, we mainly concentrate on the G-dynamics given by [5, 6]

$$\hat{w} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{-1}\hbar} [s, \hat{H}]_{QPB}$$

With the S-dynamics in the GCHS, clearly, we can say that the G-dynamics describes rotating quantum physics. There is a clear fact of the G-dynamics taken as a different form by choosing different Hamiltonian operators. Therefore, for a given wave function ψ , the eigenvalue equation of G-dynamics as an operator is accordingly given by $\hat{w}\psi = w\psi$, where w is the geometric frequency eigenvalue. It gets corresponding imaginary geomenergy expressed as

$$E^{(Im)}(\hat{w}) = \sqrt{-1}\hbar\hat{w} = [s, \hat{H}]_{QPB}$$

Thusly, it then has energy spectrum given by $E^{(Im)}\psi = \sqrt{-1}E^{(g)}\psi$, where $E^{(g)} = \hbar w$. Besides, $E^{(Im)}/\hbar = \sqrt{-1}\hat{w}$ holds in general. Obviously, we can see that the G-dynamics is completely determined by the structure function s , it implies that the G-dynamics represents the properties of the spatial manifolds.

Corollary 1. [6] *The G-dynamics in terms of the Hamiltonian operator (1) in coordinates can be expressed as*

$$\widehat{w}^{(cl)} = -\gamma_m (\Delta s + 2\nabla s \cdot \nabla) \quad (2)$$

where $\gamma_m = \frac{\sqrt{-1}\hbar}{2m}$.

Let's see how its characteristic equation shows, it's given by

$$\widehat{w}^{(cl)}\psi = -\gamma_m (\psi\Delta s + 2\nabla s \cdot \nabla\psi) = w^{(g)}\psi$$

where $\Delta = \nabla^2$. Subsequently, it derives $-\gamma_m^{-1}\widehat{w}^{(cl)} = \Delta s + 2\nabla s \cdot \nabla$, then we get the square form of the generalized gradient operator shown as

$$D^2 = \Delta + \nabla s \cdot \nabla s - \gamma_m^{-1}\widehat{w}^{(cl)} \quad (3)$$

Actually,

$$D^2 - |\nabla s|^2 = \Delta - \gamma_m^{-1}\widehat{w}^{(cl)} \quad (4)$$

as an operator is what we should mainly consider.

The one dimensional case of the G-dynamics can be written in the form

$$\widehat{w}^{(cl)}/b_c = 2u\frac{d}{dx} + \frac{d}{dx}u$$

where $b_c = -\gamma_m$, its solution for a geometric wave function $\psi = C_0\Gamma(u, w^{(g)})$ is easily obtained

$$\Gamma(u, w^{(g)}) = u^{-1/2} \exp\left(\sqrt{-1}a_c^{-1} \int \frac{w^{(g)}}{u} dx\right) \quad (5)$$

for the eigenvalues $w^{(g)}$, where $a_c = \hbar/m$ [see [6, 7] for more details].

3 Geometric quantum potential and geometric potential

In this section, we mainly discuss the geometric extension of the quantum potential under the generalized gradient operator $D = \nabla + \nabla s$ in which s can be treated as a geometric function, we shall see the connection between the quantum potential and the imaginary geomenergy in terms of the G-dynamics under a precise condition.

If we denote the quantum potential $Q^{(cl)} = a_1 \frac{\Delta A^{(b)}}{A^{(b)}}$, then by using generalized gradient operator $D = \nabla + \nabla s$, it broadly leads to the general geometric quantum potential associated with the structural function

$$Q^{(s)} = a_1 \frac{D^2 A^{(b)}}{A^{(b)}} = Q^{(cl)} + Q^{(g)}$$

where geometric potential is defined as

$$Q^{(g)} = a_1 \frac{\nabla s \cdot \nabla A^{(b)}}{A^{(b)}} + a_1 (\nabla^2 s + |\nabla s|^2)$$

where $a_1 = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m}$ is used. More precisely, it manifests the specific structure compatible with different structural energy defined on manifolds, the more detail of the geometric quantum potential can be calculated as follows

$$\begin{aligned} Q^{(s)} &= a_1 \frac{D^2 A^{(b)}}{A^{(b)}} = a_1 \frac{\Delta A^{(b)} + 2\nabla s \cdot \nabla A^{(b)} + A^{(b)} \Delta s + A^{(b)} |\nabla s|^2}{A^{(b)}} \\ &= a_1 \frac{\Delta A^{(b)}}{A^{(b)}} + 2a_1 \frac{\nabla s \cdot \nabla A^{(b)}}{A^{(b)}} + a_1 (\Delta s + |\nabla s|^2) \\ &= Q^{(cl)} + Q^{(g)} \end{aligned}$$

where the geometric potential is

$$Q^{(g)} = 2a_1 \frac{\nabla s \cdot \nabla A^{(b)}}{A^{(b)}} + T^{(c)}$$

where the structural c-energy is given by $T^{(c)} = a_1 (\Delta s + |\nabla s|^2)$. It follows the geometric quantum potential

$$Q^{(s)} = Q^{(cl)} + 2a_1 \frac{\nabla s \cdot \nabla A^{(b)}}{A^{(b)}} + T^{(c)}$$

Actually, by making use of the (3) $D^2 = \Delta + |\nabla s|^2 - \gamma_m^{-1} \widehat{w}^{(cl)}$ or G-dynamics (2), geometric quantum potential can be rewritten in a compact form

$$\begin{aligned} Q^{(s)} &= a_1 \frac{D^2 A^{(b)}}{A^{(b)}} = a_1 \frac{\Delta A^{(b)} + |\nabla s|^2 A^{(b)} - \gamma_m^{-1} \widehat{w}^{(cl)} A^{(b)}}{A^{(b)}} \\ &= a_1 \frac{\Delta A^{(b)}}{A^{(b)}} + a_1 \frac{|\nabla s|^2 A^{(b)} - \gamma_m^{-1} \widehat{w}^{(cl)} A^{(b)}}{A^{(b)}} \end{aligned}$$

It leads to the connection between the geometric potential and G-dynamics (2),

$$Q^{(g)} = a_1 \frac{|\nabla s|^2 A^{(b)} - \gamma_m^{-1} \widehat{w}^{(cl)} A^{(b)}}{A^{(b)}} = a_1 |\nabla s|^2 - \sqrt{-1} \hbar \frac{\widehat{w}^{(cl)} A^{(b)}}{A^{(b)}}$$

where $a_1 \gamma_m^{-1} = \sqrt{-1} \hbar$. As we can see that the geometric potential is only associated with the structure function s as a geometric function determined by the manifolds or the spacetime. The geometric quantum potential is also expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} Q^{(s)} &= a_1 \frac{\Delta A^{(b)}}{A^{(b)}} - \frac{\sqrt{-1} \hbar \widehat{w}^{(cl)} A^{(b)}}{A^{(b)}} + a_1 |\nabla s|^2 \\ &= (a_1 \Delta A^{(b)} - E^{(Im)} (\widehat{w}^{(cl)}) A^{(b)}) / A^{(b)} + a_1 |\nabla s|^2 \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

by using the imaginary geomenergy in terms of the G-dynamics (2).

3.1 Potenergy and motor operator

As a result of the geometric potential, let's focus on the potenergy associated with G-dynamics (2), the potenergy $E^{(wg)}$ is denoted as

$$E^{(wg)} = -\frac{\sqrt{-1} \hbar \widehat{w}^{(cl)} A^{(b)}}{A^{(b)}} = -E^{(Im)} (\widehat{w}^{(cl)}) A^{(b)} / A^{(b)}$$

Then the geometric potential is further simplified as $Q^{(g)} = a_1|\nabla s|^2 + E^{(wg)}$, meanwhile, geometric quantum potential is simply rewritten as

$$Q^{(s)} = a_1 \left(\frac{\Delta A^{(b)}}{A^{(b)}} + |\nabla s|^2 \right) + E^{(wg)}$$

Based on the geometric quantum potential (6), we can construct a new energy operator that is shown as

$$\widehat{E}^{(w)} = a_1\Delta - \sqrt{-1}\hbar\widehat{w}^{(cl)}$$

it can be called motor operator, where the imaginary geomenergy

$$E^{(\text{Im})}(\widehat{w}^{(cl)}) = \sqrt{-1}\hbar\widehat{w}^{(cl)} = \left[s, \widehat{H}^{(cl)} \right]_{QPB}$$

and $a_1\Delta = \frac{\widehat{p}^{(cl)2}}{2m}$ is the classical kinetic operator as a part of the classical Hamiltonian operator. Thusly, then the geometric quantum potential (6) rewrites $Q^{(s)} = \frac{\widehat{E}^{(w)}A^{(b)}}{A^{(b)}} + a_1|\nabla s|^2$. Notice that motor operator $\widehat{E}^{(w)}$ as an entire operator form naturally responds to (4).

By using the motor operator, the G-operator can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} \widehat{H}^{(gr)} &= \widehat{E}^{(w)} + V(x) \\ &= a_1\Delta - \sqrt{-1}\hbar\widehat{w}^{(cl)} + m\omega^2x^2/2 \\ &= \widehat{H}^{(cl)} - \sqrt{-1}\hbar\widehat{w}^{(cl)} \end{aligned}$$

in terms of classical Hamiltonian operator for classical quantum harmonic oscillator, where $V(x) = \frac{1}{2}m\omega^2x^2$ is the potential energy, $\widehat{H}^{(cl)} = a_1\Delta + \frac{1}{2}m\omega^2x^2$ is the classical Hamiltonian operator for classical quantum harmonic oscillator, then

$$\sqrt{-1}\hbar(\partial_t - \widehat{w}^{(cl)})\psi = \widehat{H}^{(gr)}\psi$$

As we discussed, the eigenvalues of the G-operator can be shown as

$$\begin{aligned} E_n^{(gr)} &= \hbar\omega(n + 1/2) - \sqrt{-1}\hbar w^{(q)} = E_n - \sqrt{-1}\hbar w^{(q)} \\ &= n\hbar\omega + E^{(hp)}, \quad n = 0, 1, 2, \dots \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} E_n &= \hbar\omega(n + 1/2), \quad n = 0, 1, 2, \dots \\ E^{(hp)} &= \hbar\omega/2 - \sqrt{-1}\hbar w^{(q)} = E_0 - \sqrt{-1}E^{(q)} \end{aligned}$$

in which $E_0 = \hbar\omega/2$ is the zero point energy for ground state, $E^{(q)} = \hbar w^{(q)}$ and $w^{(q)}$ is the frequency spectrum of the G-dynamics $\widehat{w}^{(cl)}$.

3.2 One dimensional case

Consider one dimensional case, then the geometric potential can be expressed as

$$Q^{(g)} = a_1 \left(2u \frac{d \ln A^{(b)}}{dx} + \frac{d}{dx} u \right) + a_1 u^2$$

By plugging the G-dynamics $\hat{w}^{(cl)}/b_c = 2u \frac{d}{dx} + \frac{d}{dx} u$ into above one dimensional case, and then the geometric potential rewrites

$$\begin{aligned} Q^{(g)} &= \frac{a_1}{b_c A^{(b)}} \hat{w}^{(cl)} A^{(b)} + a_1 u^2 \\ &= -\sqrt{-1} \hbar \hat{w}^{(cl)} A^{(b)} / A^{(b)} + a_1 u^2 \end{aligned}$$

where $\frac{a_1}{b_c} = -\sqrt{-1} \hbar$, and quantum potential is $Q^{(cl)} = \frac{a_1}{A^{(b)}} \frac{d^2 A^{(b)}}{dx^2}$. Accordingly, the geometric quantum potential is totally rewritten in a form

$$Q^{(s)} = \hat{E}^{(w)} A^{(b)} / A^{(b)} + a_1 u^2$$

where motor operator in one-dimensional case is

$$\hat{E}^{(w)} = a_1 \frac{d^2}{dx^2} - \sqrt{-1} \hbar \hat{w}^{(cl)}$$

3.3 A case for amplitude

Let's consider the amplitude such as $A^{(b)} = C_0 e^Z$, where Z is a complex function associated with the domain or space, on such assumption, by a direct computation, the quantum potential can be calculated accordingly, more specifically,

$$Q^{(cl)} = a_1 \frac{\nabla^2 A^{(b)}}{A^{(b)}} = a_1 \frac{C_0 \nabla^2 e^Z}{A^{(b)}} = a_1 (\nabla^2 Z + \nabla Z \cdot \nabla Z)$$

Note that if we take $Z = s$ to above quantum potential $Q^{(cl)}$, then

$$Q^{(cl)} = a_1 (\nabla^2 s + \nabla s \cdot \nabla s) \tag{7}$$

Obviously, it's equal to the structural c-energy $T^{(c)}$, that is to say, $T^{(c)} = Q^{(cl)}$ on this case. Meanwhile, we initiate the equation given by the G-dynamics (2)

$$\hat{w}^{(cl)} A^{(b)} = -\gamma_m (A^{(b)} \Delta s + 2 \nabla s \cdot \nabla A^{(b)})$$

for this case, we have

$$\hat{w}^{(cl)} A^{(b)} = C_0 \hat{w}^{(cl)} e^Z = -A^{(b)} \gamma_m (\Delta s + 2 \nabla s \cdot \nabla Z)$$

Accordingly, it yields $\hat{w}^{(cl)} A^{(b)} / A^{(b)} = -\gamma_m (\Delta s + 2 \nabla s \cdot \nabla Z)$, similarly, let $Z = s$ be given for it, then thusly, we get

$$\hat{w}^{(cl)} A^{(b)} / A^{(b)} = -\gamma_m (\Delta s + 2 \nabla s \cdot \nabla s)$$

It leads to a precise formulation of the potenergy $E^{(wg)}$

$$\begin{aligned} E^{(wg)} &= -\sqrt{-1}\hbar\hat{w}^{(cl)}A^{(b)}/A^{(b)} = \sqrt{-1}\hbar\gamma_m(\Delta s + 2\nabla s \cdot \nabla s) \\ &= a_1(\Delta s + 2\nabla s \cdot \nabla s) \\ &= a_1(\Delta s + \nabla s \cdot \nabla s) + a_1\nabla s \cdot \nabla s \end{aligned}$$

Then as mentioned above, it definitely shows a relation

$$E^{(wg)} = -\sqrt{-1}\hbar\hat{w}^{(cl)}A^{(b)}/A^{(b)} = Q^{(cl)} - E^{(s)}/2$$

or equivalently,

$$Q^{(cl)} = E^{(s)}/2 - \sqrt{-1}\hbar\hat{w}^{(cl)}A^{(b)}/A^{(b)}$$

It reveals the deep connection between the potenergy and the quantum potential under this case, where $E^{(s)} = \frac{\hbar^2}{m}\nabla s \cdot \nabla s$, and $Q^{(cl)}$ is given by (7). In this case, the quantum potential as a part can be induced by the potenergy. The geometric quantum potential (6)

$$Q^{(s)} = a_1\frac{\Delta A^{(b)}}{A^{(b)}} + E^{(wg)} + a_1|\nabla s|^2$$

in this case, the geometric quantum potential can be rewritten as $Q^{(s)} = 2Q^{(cl)} - E^{(s)}$. In other words,

$$Q^{(cl)} + a_1|\nabla s|^2 = E^{(wg)}$$

4 Conclusions

In this paper, we generalize the quantum potential to a complete version—the geometric quantum potential which contains the geometric potential as a new quantum potential which naturally contains the imaginary geomenergy and quantum potential by using the generalized gradient operator. By deeply studying, we present the concepts such as the potenergy, motor operator, etc to discuss the intrinsic relation with the imaginary geomenergy under a condition as we assumed, meanwhile, we have proved that the structural c-energy is equal to the quantum potential in such case, it states the validity of the join of the environment.

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